

ORGANIZATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF EDUCATIONAL CENTERS IN CLUSTER CONDITIONS ON THE BASE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *In this article, the organization and development of the educational process based on digital technologies in the conditions of the educational cluster is highlighted as a pedagogical problem. It was also mentioned what should be paid special attention to in order to effectively use digital technologies in the educational process while maintaining the quality of teaching.*

Keywords: *cluster approach, educational centers, E.P. Belan, "GovTech Maturity Index 2022", digital technology, educational institutions, student, parents.*

Application of the cluster approach to the pedagogic education system, especially within educational centers, is one of the current issues. Improving the educational cluster model, as well as organizing and developing the educational process on the basis of digital technologies, is currently one of the important factors in order to eliminate some problems in educational centers. It is important to have optimal cooperation of all interested parties in improving the educational cluster model in educational centers. It includes institutions that interact with each other. Integrating the team, resources and coherent system of each institution within the framework of the cluster will expand opportunities for comprehensive quality education for our youth, as well as solve a number of pedagogical problems.

According to the Russian researcher E.P. Belan, the organizational form of the cluster provides benefits for all institutions that are part of the cluster, this makes it possible to combine their efforts and increase the efficiency of the educational system, to strengthen the individualization of education and to create an integrated educational environment. In turn, the cluster model is associated with mutual obligations and joint activities of the cooperative institutions.

The organization and development of the educational process based on digital technologies in the conditions of the educational cluster is able to systematically solve some of the problems of the children in the society. Of course, through these approaches, in order to improve the cluster process in the educational process and achieve effective results, it is organized by a team of specialists and teachers who are ready to work with students in an individual integrated direction in each educational institution.

According to the "GovTech Maturity Index 2022" report compiled by the World Bank, Uzbekistan took 43rd place among 198 countries in the international ranking of information technology development in the public sector. It can be seen that our country has significantly

improved its position compared to 2020: it has risen to 37 places. In particular, according to the "GovTech Enablers" index of digital skills and innovations in public services, Uzbekistan took the 4th place in the world (increased by 65 places compared to 2020).

Judging by the information given above, we can see that digital technologies are rapidly entering our lives. Today, digital technologies are actively used in all spheres of life. It is possible to widely introduce digital technologies in state and community management, social sphere, increase efficiency, in a word, dramatically improve people's lives. It is not surprising that the educational system today is immersed in digital technologies, because it serves as a basis for serious analysis and pedagogical justification of many things that are offered in the information space today. It is also known that in recent years, several state projects or surveys have been conducted to solve the problems of "digitalization" of education. It should be noted that earlier we were limited to the implementation of digital technologies in certain areas. Today, taking into account that digital technologies are rapidly developing, they are included in all areas of digital development, especially in the field of education.

Today's classrooms are very different from ten years ago, and classrooms are equipped with computers, televisions, smart boards, and other types of educational technology. As in other parts of the world, digital technologies are emerging in Uzbekistan. As a result of constant interaction with such digital technologies, the thinking of today's youth is radically different from the way it used to be. It is necessary to adapt the educational system to the digital generation through mass and effective use of innovative educational technologies based on modern information and communication technologies. At the same time, it is necessary to actively use a research-based approach in the educational process. Through this, it is possible to develop the skills of young people and form creative thinking based on IT. Digital technologies are not a solution to all problems in the education system, but a means of making the learning process rich in information and interactive for the digital generation.

It is already known that the organization and development of the educational process based on digital technologies is considered a widely used concept, and it is a novelty that ensures the growth of the quality and efficiency of the processes required by the tireless researchers. This is the result of human intellectual activity and imagination. Digital technologies play an important role in scientific research. The implementation of digital technologies in the educational system will improve the quality of education on the basis of a cluster. It should be noted that education is a system of skills acquired by a person in pedagogical activities, and skills are considered a collection of knowledge, which can be achieved in educational institutions or with the help of independent learning. So, there is no doubt that independent education through digital technologies can further improve the quality of education in our country

In the age of information, the main task in the formation of the state's innovative capabilities in the educational process falls on teachers. Such an important task can be solved only by a teacher who has mastered modern pedagogical and information technologies, improves his knowledge, skills and abilities, has a creative approach to his work, and constantly works on himself individually. While the times are rapidly developing, education does not stand still. Now, according to the demand of the times, traditional forms of education have been replaced by non-traditional forms of education. Lessons organized through such forms of education are liked by students, arouse their interest, give them a lot of news and motivate them to move forward. Modern education sets goals for the student: free acquisition of knowledge, knowing how to

interact with different people in different situations, and at the same time feeling free and confident. For the development of the student's knowledge, skills and abilities, it is necessary to properly organize his activities. Development does not take place in the process of slow comprehension of educational material. The student's own actions will be the basis for the formation of his abilities in the future. Therefore, the task of education is to create situations that encourage students to act. In a word, teachers need to create special educational conditions that help each student to form individual tools and methods to solve tasks correctly in different situations. This, in turn, is considered one of the important issues of the technology of achieving the results set before the educational system. Digital technologies are very important in the development of the educational process.

The use of digital technologies helps to increase the interests of students and to form their positive motivation, because it takes into account the individual educational opportunities and needs of students, wide opportunities to choose the content and forms of educational activities, reveals the creative potential of students, and helps students master modern information technologies. That's why our research is the organization and development of the educational process based on digital technologies in the conditions of the educational cluster, as well as, educational centers, educational institutions, parents of the student, as well as the individual work process of the young people in question. In this case, the possibilities of digital technologies can be used to organize digital educational resources, individual tests and distance lessons.

Formation of the national system of information, mass introduction and use of modern information technologies, computer equipment and telecommunications in all spheres of economy and social life, more complete satisfaction of the growing information needs of citizens, access to the world information community and use of world information resources in order to create favorable conditions for expansion, we must start active use of digital technologies in the educational process.

The use of various technologies in the modern education system of our country allows solving the existing problem in the educational process based on a new approach. For this purpose, special attention should be paid to the implementation of information and communication technologies in the educational process.

Today's students do not want to study in a traditional way, on the contrary, they support innovative education based on modern information and communication technologies. Therefore, digitization of the education system through mass and effective use of information technologies is the need of the hour. Now the teachers do not teach in the usual way. Because, as in developed countries, a generation with high intellectual potential is growing up in Uzbekistan. The way of thinking and receiving information of young people growing up in such an environment is fundamentally different from the previous thinking and learning process.

In conclusion, there is no doubt that the use of digital technologies in the educational process will have a positive effect on the quality of education in our country. In particular, interest in the use of innovative technologies in the education system and attention to the introduction of modern methods is growing day by day. The reason is that earlier the educational goal was focused on the acquisition and memorization of ready-made knowledge. Now modern technologies are teaching them to search for knowledge by themselves and draw independent conclusions.

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